

Analysis of the Effect Work from Home and Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction with the Moderation Role of the Work Environment

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Abstract:- Work From Home (WFH) a work system that changes the culture and work procedures of employees who previously worked in offices to move to their homes. Changes to this work system can result in a lack of employee job satisfaction, in addition to that, work-life balance (WLB) and work environment (WE) also affect employee job satisfaction. The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of work from home and work-life balance of IT employees working in the Jabodetabek area on job satisfaction. This study also uses the work environment as a moderating variable. The method used in this study used a questionnaire with a sample of 205 employees working at home in the Greater Jakarta area. Data analysis used descriptive statistics using Smart PLS 3 and using quantitative types.

Keywords:- Work From Home (WFH), Work-Life Balance (WLB), Work Environment (WE), Job Satisfaction (JS).

I. BACKGROUND

Human resources play an important role for companies to achieve goals. Employees are an important asset as a determinant of organizational success, therefore a company must pay attention to its employees so that they are able to continue to work well. Job satisfaction is a factor [1]. Job satisfaction is the most important thing that every employee must have, the existence of job satisfaction can affect productivity and the results of good employee performance to achieve company goals. Job satisfaction can be the level where an employee feels happy and satisfied with his job [2]. Job satisfaction shows the emotional stability and positive attitude of employees towards their work and is an important factor for motivating employee work so that job satisfaction measures the extent to which employees are happy with their jobs [3]. However, when the Covid-19 outbreak entered Indonesia, it was difficult for companies in the Jabodetabek level 4 area to operate due to remote restrictions that the community had to carry out, therefore many companies implemented a work from home policy so that company operations continued and employees could still work as usual [4]. The implementation of Work from home was carried out on a large scale during the Covid-19 pandemic, where the government issued a PPKM policy so that companies continued to operate, WFH was implemented in

various companies. This resulted in changes in the work culture of employees working with the WFO system and having to adapt to the WFH system. On the other hand, employees who work from home have 2 roles, namely between work and personal life.

On the other hand, employees are unique individuals, employees have a need to motivate their performance, one of which is job satisfaction. The loss of employee job satisfaction will have an impact on the company's business processes [5]. Employees who are dissatisfied with the work from home system will be filled with dissatisfaction and have a negative effect on the company and even cause losses to the company. One of the perceived losses is the decrease in employee performance. This bad thing can be caused by low employee job satisfaction. This can be overcome if you get a work-life balance [6].

Work-life balance interpreted as a balance of two different roles between work and individual life and provides one's life satisfaction when carrying out these two roles [7]. Work-life balance is an illustration of the concept where a person can balance between work and personal life. In a sense, work-life balance can make a person who works able to pursue a role between work and personal life that is equally important and becomes his responsibility, such as the needs of his family, children and wife [8].

In addition to work from home, work-life balance, the physical work environment is a supporting factor and is important for achieving job satisfaction. This study uses work environment variables as aspects that encourage employees to achieve job satisfaction. A conducive work environment can provide a sense of security and comfort to employees at work because a work environment that is in line with employee expectations is able to provide job satisfaction to these employees [9].

The impact of working from home based on data obtained from Jobstreet 2020 of employees who are required to work from home, some employees work longer hours (50%) then for a longer duration and almost half (48%) have changed their working hours and/ or doing more household chores (47%) as shown in the graph below.

Fig 1 Work from Home Graph
Source: Jobstreet 2020

Jobstreet conducted a survey of 17,623 correspondents in early October regarding employee job satisfaction with their jobs. The survey results show that 73% of employees are dissatisfied with their work due to several factors. Several factors influence employee dissatisfaction with their work, namely as many as 54% of employees work not in accordance with their educational background, besides that, as many as 60% of employees admit that it is difficult to

have a career path in the company where they work, besides that, 85% of employees admit that they do not have a job-life balance, plus as many as 53% of employees admit to having a boss with a military leadership style, and also paternalist (never giving opportunities to subordinates to develop their creative power) so that they let their subordinates work as they wish, positions are only symbols and never want to know. This can be seen in the table below

Table 1 Survey of Employee Dissatisfaction with their Work

S No.	Statement	Mark
1	Employees Are Dissatisfied with their Jobs	73%
2	Employees Work Not in Accordance with their Educational Background	54%
3	Do Not have a Career Path in the Company	60%
4	Do Not have a Work-Life Balance	85%
5	Boss with a Military Leadership Style, and Also Paternalist	53%

Source: Jobstreet 2022

Therefore, it is interesting for researchers to conduct research related to the problem of employee job satisfaction in the Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Bekasi areas.

II. LITERATURE

A. Work from Home (WFH)

The term work from home first appeared in 1950 by Norbert Wiener in the book *The Human Use of Human Beings Cybernetics and Society* [10]. Work from home (WFH) is a remote work system or it can also be called remote work, the application of a remote work system, namely individuals carry out their work activities from home so that employees no longer have to come to the office to work.

B. Work-Life Balance (WLB)

Work-life balance is defined as a balance of two different roles between work and individual life and provides one's life satisfaction when carrying out these two roles[11]. Work-life balance is an illustration of the concept where a person can balance between work and personal life. In a sense, work-life balance can enable someone who works to work on a role between work and personal life that is equally important and becomes his responsibility, such as the needs of his family, children and wife [11].

C. Work Environment (WE)

The physical work environment is a supporting factor and is important for achieving job satisfaction. This study uses work environment variables as aspects that encourage

employees to achieve job satisfaction. A conducive work environment can provide a sense of security and comfort to employees at work because a work environment that is in accordance with employee expectations is able to provide job satisfaction to these employees[12]

D. Job Satisfaction (JS)

Job satisfaction is defined as the level at which an employee feels happy and satisfied with his job [13]. So job satisfaction refers to how employees feel about their jobs [14]. Job satisfaction shows the emotional stability and positive attitude of employees towards their work and is an

important factor for motivating employee work so that job satisfaction measures the extent to which employees are happy with their jobs [14].

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

Based on the background that has been described, the researcher draws pictures to facilitate understanding of the direction of research on the effect of work from home and work-life balance on job satisfaction with the moderation role of the work environment as outlined in the conceptual framework in Figure 2.

Fig 2 Conceptual Framework

➤ *Based on the Description Above, there are Four Hypotheses in this Study, Namely:*

- *H1: Work From Home has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction*
- *H2: Work-Life Balance has a positive and significant effect on Job Satisfaction*
- *H3: The work environment moderates the relationship between Work From Home and Job Satisfaction*
- *H4 : The work environment moderates the relationship between Work-Life Balance on Job Satisfaction*

III. RESEARCH AND METHODS

The method used in this research is quantitative analysis. The data collection used was distributing questionnaires to 205 respondents in the Jakarta, Bogor, Depok, Bekasi areas. Researchers used the Partial Least Square (PLS) technique and used the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) research model processed using SmartPLS to validate measurements and structural models.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Respondents collected in this study were 205 of them, 147 male respondents or a percentage of 71.7% and 58 female respondents with a percentage of 28.3%. The most areas are Tangerang 41.5%, Jakarta 36.1%, Depok 10.7%, Bogor 7.8% and Bekasi 3.9%

Table 2 Outer Loading

<u>Variabel</u>	Indicator	Job Satisfaction	Work Environment	Work from home	Work from home*Work Environment	Work-life balance	Work-life balance*Work Environment
Job Satisfaction	JS1	0,814					
	JS10	0,823					
	KJS11	0,828					
	JS2	0,833					
	JS3	0,805					
	JS4	0,837					
	JS5	0,837					
	JS6	0,825					
	JS7	0,819					
	JS8	0,802					
JS9	0,797						
Work Environment	WE1		0,886				
	WE2		0,856				
	WE3		0,874				
	WE4		0,862				
	WE5		0,874				
	WE6		0,855				
	WE7		0,871				
Work From Home	WFH1			0,812			
	WFH10			0,792			
	WFH11			0,796			
	WFH12			0,809			
	WFH13			0,781			
	WFH14			0,799			
	WFH2			0,826			
	WFH3			0,824			
	WFH4			0,793			
	WFH5			0,79			
	WFH6			0,788			
	WFH7			0,806			
WFH8			0,839				
WFH9			0,792				
Work-Life Balance	WLB1					0,838	
	WLB2					0,877	
	WLB3					0,801	
	WLB4					0,816	
	WLB5					0,84	
	WLB6					0,815	
	WLB7					0,83	
	WLB8					0,82	

Markloading factor from each indicator and its dimensions are valued above 0.7, all indicators of Job Satisfaction (Y) used in this study can be declared valid and meet the requirements of convergent validity.

Table 3 Cross Loading

<u>Variabel</u>	Indicator	Job Satisfaction	Work Environment	Work from home	Work from home*Work Environment	Work-life balance	Work-life balance*Work Environment
Job Satisfaction	JS1	0,814	0,46	0,373	0,16	0,401	0,053
	JS10	0,823	0,45	0,4	0,154	0,458	0,125
	KJS11	0,828	0,442	0,462	0,078	0,512	0,09
	JS2	0,833	0,449	0,458	0,102	0,41	0,096
	JS3	0,805	0,516	0,475	0,106	0,466	0,089
	JS4	0,837	0,429	0,435	0,148	0,405	0,121
	JS5	0,837	0,488	0,465	0,079	0,498	0,081
	JS6	0,825	0,481	0,468	0,043	0,37	0,069
	JS7	0,819	0,53	0,448	0,078	0,38	0,101
	JS8	0,802	0,451	0,437	0,086	0,33	0,165
JS9	0,797	0,427	0,454	0,122	0,445	0,113	
Work Environment	WE1	0,534	0,886	0,429	-0,123	0,265	-0,035
	WE2	0,472	0,856	0,412	-0,175	0,271	-0,087
	WE3	0,506	0,874	0,43	-0,159	0,252	-0,022
	WE4	0,467	0,862	0,449	-0,181	0,266	-0,021
	WE5	0,499	0,874	0,448	-0,176	0,266	-0,02
	WE6	0,478	0,855	0,416	-0,138	0,264	-0,003
	WE7	0,497	0,871	0,44	-0,199	0,233	-0,003
Work From Home	WFH1	0,424	0,431	0,812	-0,378	0,285	0,045
	WFH10	0,363	0,319	0,792	-0,348	0,276	0,052
	WFH11	0,442	0,37	0,796	-0,283	0,358	0,053
	WFH12	0,482	0,445	0,809	-0,338	0,405	0,019
	WFH13	0,415	0,403	0,781	-0,25	0,32	0,046
	WFH14	0,388	0,393	0,799	-0,396	0,288	-0,016
	WFH2	0,497	0,411	0,826	-0,304	0,362	0,084
	WFH3	0,472	0,444	0,824	-0,277	0,33	0,063
	WFH4	0,444	0,395	0,793	-0,313	0,298	0,101
	WFH5	0,444	0,356	0,79	-0,231	0,359	0,041
	WFH6	0,43	0,408	0,788	-0,254	0,361	0,053
	WFH7	0,426	0,426	0,806	-0,343	0,391	-0,016
	WFH8	0,417	0,412	0,839	-0,38	0,392	-0,012
WFH9	0,412	0,364	0,792	-0,328	0,328	0,041	
Work-Life Balance	WLB1	0,458	0,239	0,372	0,047	0,838	-0,032
	WLB2	0,488	0,257	0,361	0,065	0,877	-0,089
	WLB3	0,425	0,263	0,341	-0,012	0,801	-0,106
	WLB4	0,395	0,176	0,32	0,065	0,816	-0,043
	WLB5	0,409	0,266	0,322	0,036	0,84	-0,126
	WLB6	0,394	0,229	0,304	0,082	0,815	-0,131
	WLB7	0,475	0,314	0,403	0,02	0,83	-0,116
	WLB8	0,396	0,227	0,385	-0,024	0,82	-0,1
Work from home * Work Environment	WFH*WE	0,127	-0,188	-0,391	1,000	0,042	0,336
Work-life balance * Work Environment	WLB*WE	0,121	-0,032	0,05	0,336	-0,111	1,000

Based on the results of the data that can be seen in table 3 above, it can be seen that the correlation of each indicator in the research variable has a higher cross loading value than the correlation of other indicators.

Table 4 Cross Loading

Construct Reliability and Validity	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Information
Job satisfaction	0,673	Valid
Work environment	0,754	Valid
Work from home	0,646	Valid
Work from home* Work environment	1,000	Valid
Work-life balance	0,689	Valid
Work-life balance* Work environment	1,000	Valid

Based on the results of the data that can be seen in Table 4, the value of the square root of average variance extracted (AVE) is said to be good because it must be greater than 0.5

Table 5 Composite Reliability & Cronbach's Alpha

Construct Reliability and Validity	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Information
Job Satisfaction	0,951	0,958	Reliabel
Work environment	0,946	0,955	Reliabel
Work from home	0,958	0,962	Reliabel
Work from home*Work environment	1,000	1,000	Reliabel
Work-life balance	0,935	0,947	Reliabel
Work-life balance*Work environment	1,000	1,000	Reliabel

Based on the results in table 5, it shows that the results of the test composite reliability and cronbach's alpha above 0.70. This states that all latent variables are said to be reliable.

Table 6 R-Square

	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted
Job satisfaction (Y)	0,587	0,577

Based on the results in table 6 it shows that the r square value of Job Satisfaction is 0.587. So it can be concluded that the effect of Work from Home, Work-life Balance, Work environment, Work environment*Work from Home, and Work environment*Work-life Balance on Job Satisfaction is 58.7%. The rest is explained by other variables.

Table 7 Q-Square

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Job satisfaction	2.255.000	1.405.681	0.377
Work environment	1.435.000	1.435.000	0.000
Work from Home	2.870.000	2.870.000	0.000
Work-life Balance	1.640.000	1.640.000	0.000

Based on The results in Table 7 show that the predictive relevance Q2 value of the endogenous latent variable Job Satisfaction is 0.377 or greater than 0. It can be concluded that the model already has predictive relevance.

$$GoF = AVE \times R^2$$

$$Average AVE = (0.673+0.754+0.646+1+0.689+1) / 6 = 0.7936$$

R2 =0.587

GoF = 0.79367 x0.587 = 0.4658823

Based on the calculation of Goodness of Fit (GoF) the calculation result is 0.4658823. Thus, the calculation between the outer model and the inner model has a large GoF above 0.36.

Table 8 Direct Effects

Hipotesis	Influence	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information
H1	<i>Work from home > Job satisfaction</i>	3,513	0	Significance
H2	<i>Work-life balance > Job satisfaction</i>	2,49	0,013	Significance
H3	<i>Work from home* Work environment > Job satisfaction</i>	2,31	0,021	Significance
H4	<i>Work-life balance* Work environment > Job satisfaction</i>	0,213	0,831	Not Significance

The results of the table above show that Work from home has a significant positive effect on Job Satisfaction because the t statistics value is 3.513 which is greater than t table = 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value and also a p value of 0.000 which is smaller than 0, 05 so that the first hypothesis is accepted.

The test results show that the t statistics value is 2.490 which is greater than t table = 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value and also a p value of 0.013 which is smaller than 0.05 so that the second hypothesis is accepted. This proves that work-life balance has a positive effect on job satisfaction.

The third hypothesis tests whether the work environment can moderate work from home on job satisfaction. The test results show a t statistics value of 2.310 which is greater than t table = 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value and also a p value of 0.021 which is less than 0.05. So the third hypothesis is accepted. This proves that the work environment can moderate the work from home relationship on job satisfaction.

The test results show that the t statistics value is 0.213 which is smaller than t table = 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value and also a p value of 0.831 which is greater than 0.05. So the fourth hypothesis is rejected. This proves that the work environment cannot moderate the work-life balance relationship on job satisfaction.

Based on hypothesis testing in this study, The results of this analysis show that there is a positive and significant effect of work from home on employee job satisfaction. This suggests that when employees work at home or. work from home can increase employee job satisfaction. Job satisfaction

is a feeling of satisfaction that employees get from the tasks and work they do. These results are in line with previous studies which state that work from home has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. Which means, the higher the effectiveness of employees working at home, the higher their job satisfaction. [15][16][17][18][19].

There is a positive and significant influence *work-life balance* on job satisfaction. This suggests that the more the company pays attention to the work balance of its employees, it tends to increase employee job satisfaction. These results are in line with previous research which states that work-life balance has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction. That is, Employees have flexibility and autonomy in balancing their work and personal lives and tend to increase their job satisfaction. [20][21][22][23][24].

The work environment can moderate relationships *work from home* on job satisfaction. These results prove that the Work Environment can moderate Work From Home on Job Satisfaction. It can be interpreted that with a Work Environment the effect of Work From Home on Job Satisfaction is getting higher. The existence of a good and adequate work environment such as facilities to support work, good relations between employees and superiors or good relations between employees, then employees can get job satisfaction or it can be said that the lack of a good and adequate work environment will trigger employees to feel dissatisfied with their work. . These results are confirmed by previous studies [25][26].

Based on the results of the fourth hypothesis test that the work environment cannot moderate the work-life balance relationship on job satisfaction. In this case, based on the respondents' answers from the questionnaire which stated that due to the lack of close good relations of mutual

respect and respect for superiors and subordinates, it is likely that employees are always under pressure at work. These results are not in line with research which states that the work environment moderates the relationship between work-life balance on job satisfaction [27].

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The more effective the implementation *work from home* done then can maintain employee job satisfaction. The lowest indicator for the work from home variable is the WFH 14 indicator, where employees while working from home do not have free time to do other work such as private tutoring, online tutoring, online business to supplement their financial income. So it is recommended that employees make a work schedule for work from home and other work so that these two jobs can be managed smoothly, in addition to that it is suggested for companies to make a special schedule for work from home employees so that it motivates employees to complete their work according to the allotted time.

Conclusion regarding *work-life balance* positive effect on job satisfaction. The highest indicator in this study is the Time Balance dimension with the indicator I can make good use of time in completing work assignments and family obligations. This shows that employees can carry out 2 different roles, namely being responsible for their work and being responsible for their family. , so that employees can balance between work and personal life. While the lowest indicator is on the indicator I use time outside of work for activities with family, where employees do not have time to carry out activities with family due to work that must be completed by employees. So it is recommended that employees can set priorities for work.

Conclusion regarding The work environment can moderate the work from home relationship on job satisfaction. The highest indicator of the equipment dimension is that the office has provided complete equipment to support my work. So far, the company continues to provide work facilities and equipment needed to support employee performance. So it is recommended that companies always upgrade employee work equipment, especially work from home employees such as old laptops/PCs, increase the internet network so that the internet connection remains stable, and other office work tools

The conclusion regarding the work environment cannot moderate the work-life balance relationship on job satisfaction. The lowest indicator of the dimension Work Process is lack of good relationship of mutual respect and respect superiors with their subordinates. Suggestions for companies to apply code of conduct regulations properly to superiors and employees so that good relations between employees and superiors are maintained so as to create a comfortable and safe work atmosphere to maintain employee job satisfaction

In this study the value of r-square 0.587 means 58.7% Job satisfaction is influenced by variables *work from home*, *work-life balance*, and work environment, the remaining 42.3% is explained by other variables, so it is suggested that this research be developed by adding other variables that affect job satisfaction such as organizational culture, family environment and work stress.

Suggestions for further research are to use interview methods or direct observation of the respondents, so that the answers obtained from the respondents can be controlled and the respondents do not misperceive the questionnaire used.

In this study using objects in the Jabodetabek area, the suggestion for further research is to add broader research objects such as throughout the island of Java so that the answers received from respondents are more varied.

Suggestions for further research are to use other types of industries that can be done from home in order to enrich research *work from home* and work-life balance on job satisfaction.

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